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Research Article

**STUDY TO EVALUATE ANXIETY AND DEPRESSION AMONG
STUDENTS OF A MEDICAL COLLEGE IN LAHORE,
PAKISTAN****¹Dr. Muhammad Majid Kanwar, ² Dr. Aneeqa Tahir, ³ Dr. Asamah Ramzan**¹Shifa Tameer e Millat University Islamabad²Services Institute Of Medical Sciences, Lahore³RHC Farooq a bad Tehsil and District Sheikhpura**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

Objective : To evaluate predominance of uneasiness and dejection among restorative understudies in a Services Institute Of Medical Sciences lahore Techniques : A cross-sectional investigation was done on premedical, first, second and third year understudies of Services Institute of Medical Sciences Lahore, The instrument used to survey the tension and despondency was Self managed poll, The Aga Khan University Anxiety and Depression Scale (AKUADS). AKUADS is a screening instrument, and at a cut off purpose of 19, it has a Specificity of 81%, Sensitivity of 74%, a Positive Predictive Value of 63% and Negative Predictive Value of 88%. Information examination was done on Epi Info form 6.

Results : At the season of the investigation there were a sum of 288 male understudies and 105 female understudies tried out the school. The general reaction rate among the guys and females were 68.7% and 99.0% individually. In general the pervasiveness of nervousness and discouragement in females were 66.6% and guys 44.4% (p -esteem 0.01). In the first year the commonness in females were 89.7% and guys 60% (P -Value = 0.006). No self-destructive ideation was accounted for by either guys or females.

End : Almost comparative dimension of nervousness and dejection was found in another investigation utilizing a similar instrument in a comparative educational modules model therapeutic school in Pakistan. Our discoveries are likewise predictable with the discoveries from different investigations from western therapeutic schools just as other Asian and African medicinal schools utilizing distinctive screening devices.

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INTRODUCTION:

Despondency and tension dimensions in the network are considered as significant pointers for emotional wellness. A few examinations have reported worry among restorative understudies extending from 12% to 73%.

A cross-sectional examination done by the creator on 189 therapeutic understudies in a Pakistani medicinal school with an issue based incorporated network arranged educational modules uncovered a general pervasiveness rate of 60% with second year understudies having a predominance of 73%. (13) An investigation from Zimbabwe led on first year understudies following 7 months passage in the restorative school discovered 64.5% of understudies had different dimensions of pressure including despondency. (15) Study from United Arab Emirates University, Al-Ain likewise detailed 65% predominance of worry among restorative understudies. (9) An investigation (6) was done on 140 Hong Kong Chinese understudies in the second year of their restorative training and contrasted with 138 understudies overviewed earlier with starting their first year of therapeutic school and with 74 non-medicinal college understudies in their second year found that in medicinal understudies trouble as pondered in their scores uneasiness and sadness self-report scales was high, and these understudies announced more prominent use of wellbeing proficient administrations as contrasted and the other two gatherings. The examination likewise demonstrated that there was no contrast between the genders with respect to the advancement of tension and melancholy indications. Another examination (11) to decide occurrence of stress and figures controlling pressure restorative understudies at different phases of MBBS course was done on 238 understudies (First year 98, Second 76, Third 64). The investigation demonstrated that 73% of medicinal understudies apparent pressure, and stress was observed to be altogether more in Second and Third MBBS understudies as opposed to First MBBS levels. The investigation did not demonstrate any noteworthy sexual orientation contrast in understudies with pressure.

In a planned report (16), all first-year college understudies of one therapeutic school were given a nitty gritty, self-report survey and another in the second year. They were approached to finish the General Health Questionnaire (GHQ), the Spielberger State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) and the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI). The outcomes demonstrated that mental test scores on the GHQ, the STAI and the BDI climbed fundamentally in

medicinal understudies between the first and second years. Another imminent investigation (17) was done on 304 first-and second-year therapeutic understudies evaluated for dejection with a month to month Beck Depression Inventory (BDI). Understudies scoring over nine on the BDI and a control bunch were then met with the NIMH Diagnostic Interview Schedule. The examination found that the occurrence of real melancholy or plausible real misery by DSM-III criteria amid the initial two years of restorative school was 12%. The lifetime predominance was 15%, multiple times more prominent than the rate in the all-inclusive community. The reason for this examination is to discover the pervasiveness of tension and gloom among understudies of Services Institute of Medical Sciences lahore.

METHODS:

Site: The investigation site is the Institute of Services Medical Sciences Lahore to present network situated medicinal instruction with and coordinated framework and an issue-based learning approach. It has a multi year restorative educational programs with an extra one year of premedical. At the season of the examination there were 105 female understudies and 288 male understudies.

Study structure: It is a cross-sectional investigation utilizing a self-managed poll. The filling of poll was deliberate and was managed to all understudies present in the class. The individuals who were missing were pursued twice.

Information accumulation instrument: The instrument utilized for screening for nervousness and sadness is the Aga Khan University Anxiety and Depression Scale (AKUADS). It has been approved on a factually proper example estimate, in urban squatter settlement of Karachi. (18) It was created from the grievances of 150 on edge and discouraged patients. The poll has 25 things, 13 mental and 12 substantial, which builds its unwavering quality for use as a screening instrument on the grounds that the greater part of the accessible instruments contains either mental or physical things. At a cut off score of 19 points AKUADS has explicitness of 81%, affectability of 74%, a positive prescient estimation of 63%, and negative prescient estimation of 88%. (18)

Information Analysis: The information was entered and broke down utilizing Epi data rendition 6.0. Recurrence tables were created and Chi Square trial of essentialness was connected on the outcomes got.

RESULTS

The reaction rate among the females were

27/28(96.4%), 29/29 (100%), 29/29 (100%) and 19/19 (100%) in the premedical, first, second and third years separately. The reaction rate among the guys were 49/84 (58.3%), 40/71 (56.3%), 57/77 (74.0%) and 52/56 (92.8%) in the premedical, first, second and third years separately. The general reaction rate among females and guys were 99.0% and 68.7% individually. In general, the predominance of nervousness and wretchedness in the females is higher (60.6%) than the guys (44.4%), P -esteem <0.01 (see Fig. 1). No self-destructive ideation was found in any reaction from the two guys and females.

Contrast in the rate of uneasiness and among male and female understudies were noteworthy just in the first year (89.7%) among female versus 60% male ($p= 0.014$). First year females were 5.8 occasions bound to have nervousness and despondency than first year guys (95% CI = 1.3, 28.7). In every single other year, contrasts among male and female understudies were not huge. In the two sexes, the most noteworthy commonness was in the first year (as portrayed above, trailed by pre-medicinal, third year and second year individually observe Table (1).

Fig. (1). Depression according to Gender.

Table (1). Depression according to Gender and Year.

Students	Female		Male		P-Value
	No.	Depressed	No.	Depressed	
Pre Medical	27	17 (63.0%)	49	20 (40.8%)	0.064
Ist Year	29	26 (89.7%)	40	24 (60.0%)	0.006
2 nd Year	29	7 (24.1%)	57	18 (31.6%)	0.472
3rd Year	19	13 (68.4%)	52	26 (50.0%)	0.167

Wretchedness were altogether higher in first year female understudies (89.7 %) when contrasted with first year male understudies (60 %), $P= 0.006$. The distinction in predominance rates of tension and melancholy between "years" were huge in the two females ($p<0.001$) and guys ($p=0.03$). Be that as it may, no year-related pattern was distinguished in the information and chi square test for pattern investigation was non-convincing (see Fig 2). Melancholy was fundamentally higher in Female 60.6% when contrasted with Male 44.4 $P<0.01$.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

The predominance rates while higher among females differ by year albeit no set example was recognized. Understudies of the two sexual orientations were observed to be most discouraged in their first year, trailed by third year, pre-restorative and second year.

Tension and discouragement can be taken as a dependable marker for appraisal of psychological instability in the network. (13) The decision of utilizing AKUADS for screening was on the grounds that it has been utilized in comparative settings and that it is approved in a general public with Islamic social qualities. A few thinks about have revealed trouble among medicinal understudies (1-14,19-21), while a few investigations have found next to zero proof of worry among therapeutic understudies (22,23). In any case, as right on time as 1956, concern has been appeared passionate status of understudies amid their medicinal preparing. (24) In our investigation the commonness of tension and

wretchedness in female understudies is 60.6% and in guys is 44.4% which is high however steady with other western examinations just as concentrates from Pakistan, India, Zimbabwe and United Arab Emirates.

In this our investigation high commonness in first year understudies might be clarified by the presentation of assuming greater liability for their taking in and a move from the conventional spoon encouraging instructing approach. The drop of commonness rate in second year may bolster the above speculation since by then the understudies become acclimated to the framework. More elevated amounts of worry in females is likewise announced in western writing. (1,3) This examination likewise demonstrates more elevated amounts of nervousness and melancholy among females, while comparable examination utilizing a similar screening instrument did not discover critical sexual orientation distinction in the dimensions of uneasiness and misery.

Prevalence Rates of Depression by Gender and Year

Fig. (2). Depression levels according to gender and year of study.

(13)

The potential reasons given by various investigations are (a) females are all the more whining about the volume and intricacy of the material they needed to cover, (b) they are bound to report pressure (1), (c) inclination of females to over report medicinal and mental manifestations. (22) Nonetheless male predisposition towards female grumblings can't be discounted. Be that as it may, in our examination,

since the poll was self-managed and mysterious, in this way, further workup couldn't be done to coax out the components identified with higher announced dimensions of tension and dejection in females. Studies have additionally revealed self-destructive ideation among medicinal understudies. An across the nation planned examination from Norway (25) uncovered commonness of self-destructive musings

in 14%. The existence time pervasiveness was 43%, 8% had arranged suicide and 1.4% endeavored suicide. None of the respondents in our examination communicated self-destructive ideation. This might be clarified by the preclusion of suicide and self-destructive ideation by Quran or Islamic social qualities which may have inhibitorily affected announcing self-destructive ideation.

Different investigations have revealed substance misuse and liquor abuse among restorative understudies and junior specialists under pressure. (12, 26) Such conduct can't be discounted in the restorative network as access to drugs is moderately simpler. This examination did not investigate substance misuse. Therapeutic school educational program are requesting, broad and require elevated amounts of capabilities. Assessment of scholarly execution through constant evaluation and examinations are accounted for to be scholastic stressors. (27) In light of the distributed writing, the commonness of tension and melancholy in this investigation is high however steady with different examinations. Ramifications of stress including tension and misery are of genuine concern bringing about failure to adapt to curricular requests and freak conduct, impedance of working in homeroom execution and clinical practice. (28)

Planning medicinal understudies for life as specialists require more than obtaining of learning and aptitudes. (27) Constant observing of execution, proficient direct and conduct related with psychological well-being is similarly significant. In spite of the fact that, the subject is of prime significance yet shockingly writing hunt done by Shapiro yielded more than 600 articles talking about the significance of tending to the worry of restorative instruction, just 24 considers announced mediation programs, and just 6 of those utilized thorough logical strategy. (29) Therefore, it is significant that medicinal educationists in Pakistan further investigations to discover the commonness of nervousness and misery in other therapeutic schools, just as, different orders offering graduate projects, distinguish the stressors and address the issue by founding suitable measures.

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